

Synthesis of Thiazolidones. Part I. Synthesis of 4-Oxo-3-aryl-5-alkyl/aryl-thiazolin-2-yl-hydrazones

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Several 4-oxo-3-aryl-5-alkyl/aryl-thiazolin-2-yl-hydrazones have been synthesised from the 4-arylthiosemicarbazones by condensing them with chloroacetic, α -bromopropionic, and α -bromophenylacetic acids. These compounds have been prepared to study their physiological activities.

Several thiazolidone derivatives exhibit a wide variety of physiological activities, such as, anaesthetic¹, anticonvulsant², amebacidal³, and hypnotic⁴. 2-Arylimino-4-thiazolidones have also been found to show physiological activities⁵. Buu-Hoi *et al.*⁶ synthesised several 4-oxo- Δ^3 -thiazolin-2-yl-hydrazones possessing tuberculostatic activity. Thiazolidine ring and benzyl group are also present in Penicillin molecules.

In the light of the observations that 2-aryl-3-alkyl-4-thiazolidones⁷ show anticonvulsant properties and hydrazones of 3-alkyl-2, 4-thiazolin-diones have been found to be tuberculostatic⁷, various 4-oxo-3-aryl-5-alkyl/aryl-thiazolin-2-yl-hydrazones have been synthesised to investigate their tuberculostatic and anticonvulsant effects. A study of the physiological activities of these compounds is in progress and will be reported later.

EXPERIMENTAL

For synthesising 4-oxo-3-aryl-5-alkyl/aryl-thiazolin-2-yl-hydrazones, 4-arylthiosemicarbazides required were prepared from the corresponding isothiocyanates by the action of hydrazine hydrate in ethanol. These 4-substituted thiosemicarbazides, when condensed with various aldehydes, afforded the corresponding thiosemicarbazones. Table I describes the thiosemicarbazones prepared. The thiosemicarbazones, when treated with chloroacetic, α -bromopropionic, and α -bromophenylacetic acids in presence of fused sodium acetate according to Pavlenko⁷ and cyclised, furnished the title compounds, described in Table II.

Following processes typify the procedure followed for the synthesis of compounds described in Tables I and II.

*All m.p.s are uncorrected.

1. Surrey, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 3354.
2. Troutman and Long, *ibid.*, 1949, **70**, 3486.
3. Surrey and Cutler, *ibid.*, 1954, **76**, 578.
4. Doran and Shonke, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1938, **3**, 193.
5. Rout *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1954, **32**, 617, 701.
6. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 718.
7. *Farm. Zbir., Ktec*, 1959, No. 4, pp. 3-7.

TABLE I

Thiosemicarbazones.

R.	M.P. A. R. = Ph.	Formula.	% Sulphur.		M.P. B. R. = <i>p</i> -Tol.	Formula.	% Sulphur	
			Found.	Reqd.			Found.	Reqd.
C ₆ H ₅	189°(d)	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₃ S	12.4	13.5	173°	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ N ₃ S	11.8	11.9
<i>o</i> -HO.C ₆ H ₄	190°(f)	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ ON ₃ S	11.6	11.8	191°	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ ON ₃ S	11.2	11.2
<i>p</i> -HO.C ₆ H ₄	226°(e)	"	11.7	11.8	189°	"	11.1	11.2
<i>o</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	175°(d)	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ N ₃ S	11.8	11.9	153°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ S	11.2	11.3
<i>p</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	203°	"	11.7	11.9	277°	"	11.1	11.3
<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄	180°(e)	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ ON ₃ S	11.3	11.4	154°	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ ON ₃ S	10.7	10.7
·CH = CH.C ₆ H ₅	176°	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₃ S	11.2	11.4	180°	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₄ S	10.6	10.8
<i>m</i> -NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	194°(e)	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₄ S	10.5	10.7	218°(e)	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₄ S	10.0	10.2
2,4-O ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	179°	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₃ Cl ₃ S	9.7	9.9	206°	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ N ₃ Cl ₂ S	9.4	9.5
3,4-(CH ₃) ₂ O ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	203°	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₃ S	10.5	10.7	199°	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃ S	10.0	10.2
3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ (OH).C ₆ H ₃	190°	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₃ S	10.6	10.7	120°	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ S	10.0	10.2
4-O ₂ H ₇	196°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ S	10.4	10.5	168°	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₃ S	9.8	10.0

N. B. (e) Pulvermacher, *Ber.*, 1894, **27**, 616, (f) Pulvermacher, *loc. cit.*, reports m.p. 183°. (g) Franzer and Richter, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1861, **vi**, 82, 249, report m.p. 225°. (d) Shueh & Oppermann, *Ber.*, 1904, **37**, 2322. (e) Bose, *this Journal*, 1926, **2**, 104. (f) Fromm & Frey, *Annalen*, 1929, **434**, 396, report m.p. 169°.

TABLE II

4-Oxo-3-aryl-5-alkyl/aryl-thiazolin-2-yl-hydraczone.

R''	M.P.	Formula.	%Sulphur.		Formula.	%Sulphur.	
			Found.	Reqd.		Found.	Reqd.
C ₆ H ₅ o-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ p-OH.C ₆ H ₄ o-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ p-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ p-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ m-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ -CH=CH.C ₆ H ₅ 2,4-O ₂ .C ₆ H ₃ 3,4(OH ₂) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃ 3,4(OCH ₃) ₂ (OH).C ₆ H ₃ o-C ₁₀ H ₇	244°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ON ₂ S	10.6	10.8	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ ON ₂ S	10.3	10.4
	279°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ S	10.1	10.3	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ S	9.6	9.8
	228°	"	10.2	10.3	"	9.7	9.8
	236°	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ ON ₂ S	10.2	10.4	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ ON ₂ S	9.7	9.9
	220°	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ ON ₂ S	10.3	10.4	"	9.7	9.9
	223°	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂ S	9.7	9.9	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ S	9.2	9.4
	236°	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ S	9.2	9.4	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂ S	8.8	9.0
	233°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ON ₂ S	9.8	10.0	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ ON ₂ S	9.4	9.6
	276°	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ ON ₂ Cl ₂ S	8.6	8.8	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ ON ₂ Cl ₂ S	8.2	8.5
	249°	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂ S	9.3	9.4	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₂ S	9.0	9.0
	268°	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂ S	9.2	9.4	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ S	8.9	9.0
	275°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ON ₂ S	9.1	9.3	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ ON ₂ S	8.6	8.9

A. R = H; R' = Ph.

B. R = H; R' = p-Tol.

TABLE II (contd.)

R ¹ .	M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.		M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
			Found.	Reqd.			Found	Reqd.
		C, R=M ₆ ; R'=Ph.				D, R=M ₆ ; R'=p-Tol.		
C ₆ H ₅	190°	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ ON ₃ S	10.2	10.4	183°	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ ON ₃ S	9.7	9.9
<i>o</i> -OH.C ₆ H ₄	185°	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₃ S	9.7	9.8	108°	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ S	9.5	9.5
<i>p</i> -OH.C ₆ H ₄	228°	"	9.8	9.8	218°	"	9.3	9.5
<i>o</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	160°	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ ON ₃ S	9.8	9.9	186°	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ ON ₃ S	9.3	9.5
<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄	172°	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ S	9.3	9.4	191°	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃ S	8.8	9.0
<i>m</i> -NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	200°	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₃ S	8.9	9.0	171°	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₃ S	8.4	8.7
-CH=CH.C ₆ H ₅	..	..	..	..	200°	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ ON ₃ S	9.0	9.2
2,4-Cl ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	206°	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ ON ₃ Cl ₂ S	8.2	8.5	190°	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ ON ₃ Cl ₂ S	8.0	8.2
3,4-(CH ₃) ₂ O ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	209°	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃ S	9.0	9.0	187°	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ S	8.6	8.7
3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ (OH).C ₆ H ₃	172°	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ S	8.9	9.0	115°	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃ S	8.6	8.7
<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₇	176°	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ ON ₃ S	8.6	8.9	161°	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ ON ₃ S	8.2	8.6
		E, R=R=Ph.				F, R=Ph; R'=p-Tol.		
C ₆ H ₅	186°	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ ON ₃ S	8.6	8.9	188°	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ ON ₃ S	8.2	8.3
<i>o</i> -OH.C ₆ H ₄	232°	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ S	8.3	8.5	217°	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃ S	7.6	8.0
<i>p</i> -OH.C ₆ H ₄	179°	"	8.1	8.5	115°	"	7.6	8.0
<i>o</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	199°	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ ON ₃ S	8.1	8.3	118°	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ ON ₃ S	8.0	8.0
<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄	169°	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃ S	7.8	8.0	187°	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₃ S	7.5	7.7
-CH=CH.C ₆ H ₅	..	..	..	..	240°	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ ON ₃ S	7.6	8.0
<i>m</i> -NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	213°	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₃ S	7.5	7.7	194°	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₃ S	7.3	7.4
2,4-Cl ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	200°	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ ON ₃ Cl ₂ S	7.0	7.3	199°	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ ON ₃ Cl ₂ S	7.0	7.0
3,4-(CH ₃) ₂ O ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	215°	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ S	7.5	7.7	210°	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃ S	7.6	7.6
3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ (OH).C ₆ H ₃	187°	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃ S	7.5	7.7	310°	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₃ S	7.2	7.4
<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₇	212°	C ₂₆ H ₁₉ ON ₃ S	7.5	7.6	184°	C ₂₇ H ₂₁ ON ₃ S	7.0	7.4

4-Phenyl-1-benzylidene-thiosemicarbazide.—A solution of equimolar (0.01*M*) amounts of 4-phenylthiosemicarbazide (1.67 g.) and benzaldehyde (1.06 g.), each in ethanol (10 ml) and a few drops of glacial acetic acid, was refluxed for 2 hours. The reaction mixture on cooling yielded a product (2.3 g about 90% yield) which after washing with cold water and dilute ethanol was recrystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 189°.

4-Oxo-3,5-diphenylthiazolin-2-yl-hydrazone.—A solution of 4-phenyl-1-benzylidene-thiosemicarbazide (2.55g., 0.01*M*) and α -bromophenylacetic acid (2.15 g., 0.01*M*) in glacial acetic acid (15 ml) was refluxed with fused sodium acetate (1.25 g., 0.15 *M*) for 5 hours. The reaction product was poured in water, kept overnight and filtered to afford 4-oxo-3,5-diphenylthiazolin-2-yl-hydrazone (2.16 g., about 60% yield). It was crystallised from acetic acid to furnish colorless needles, m.p. 198°.

In most cases, 5 to 6 hours' reflux period and two crystallisations were found satisfactory.

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